

Perceived Stress and Sources of Stress among Medical Undergraduates, Lahore, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To determine the level of perceived stress and the probable stressors.

Study Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out during April 2018 in Lahore.

Materials and Methods: Convenient sampling was used. A questionnaire with 30 items and PSS-10 was completed by 500 medical students. SPSS-22 software was used for analysing the data. For analysing differences in mean perceived stress score in different groups, ANOVA technique was used. For determining the main stress element, binary Logistic Regression Analysis was performed. P-Value was set at 0.05.

Results: 90% (450/500) was the total response rate. The total mean PSS was 21.32 (SD=5.21) and was significantly high among the 1st year students with a score of 22.41 (SD=6.14). The occurrence of academic, health and psychological associated stressors were 38%, 32% and 30% respectively.

Conclusion: Perceived stress at increased level was found among fresh enrolling MBBS students. The most common stressors were the academic stressors. It is imperative for medical teachers to appreciate the level of stress and its different causes in undergraduate medical student. Therefore, an early guidance and regular assessments of stressors is suggested which will support in preparing students for stressful career of a health professional.

Key Words: Academic Stressors, Medical Students, Perceived Stress

INTRODUCTION

The perception that his/her workload is exceeding his ability to handle is the perceived stress. Globally the growing concern is that a considerable stress by medical education has been put on the students which affect their overall life quality. The life quality is badly affected by the study pressure, long stays in hospital and hectic lecture routine which is leaving students with negative changes in behaviours, some good social contacts and bad psycho-social comfort. Medical professionals are struggling for having their parents' better quality of life whereas their own routine life controvert the definition of a lifestyle which is healthy and ideal. Many stressors among students have been report which covers assessment frequency and types,

substandard nutrition, living standard in hostel, working relations, learning environment etc. Poor academic performance has been shown by the students who are more stressed and resultantly is leading toward making less competent doctor.

Depression is cause by the stress to the various stressors that is affecting the medical student's mental functioning and consequently is leading toward the bad health, thoughts of suicide and burnouts. Among medical students there is alarming percentage at increased level who have thought or attempted suicide. Therefore, it is imperative to measure stress and its different cause otherwise it may result in disastrous if these causes are not sorted out immediately. Studies on the prevalence of stress have been conducted in Brazil, Germany, India, New Zealand, Sweden, UK and USA. Stress at varying degrees was reported as the different instruments were used in conducting the studies for the stress assessment or the difference could be real because of varying backgrounds of socio-demography. Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) was used in different researches conducted in Bangladesh, Greece, India and Pakistan for assessing the stress level. This scale is used internationally for assessing the perception of psychological stress. Mean PSS score of 30.84 was assessed according to study carried out in Civil Military Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan.

Local data of epidemiology relation to social, academic, health and psychological issues in undergraduate medical students is very insignificant in number and the information is deficient relating to stress and its different sources in undergraduate medical students in Pakistan. The instant research was conducted in the undergraduate medical students of Lahore to assess the prevalence of the stress perceived in the medical undergraduates and to find out the main stressor affecting the medical undergraduates. Hypothesis: 1. There exist positive correlation between initial academic year and perceived stress. 2. Main of the likely stressors affect the academic performance of medical undergraduates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was observational descriptive cross-section survey conducted in April 2018 in students of Lahore after the approval from ethical committee. The size of the sample consisted of 450 participants for the research with expected rate of response of 90%. Randomised non-probability convenient sampling was done. Two questionnaires (PSS-10 and a stressor questionnaire with 30 items) were asked to be filled by the participants. 10 statements were made part of PSS-10 and that was rated 5 point on a Likert scale and the responder needs to tell where the thoughts range from never, almost never, sometimes, fairly-often and very often (0,1,2,3,4 respectively) in the last month. The calculation of the score was by adding up the responses marking maximum score of 40. Items 4,5,7, and 8 are positively stated and their calculation of score was by the reverse coding the items (0=4, 1=3, 2=2, 3=1, 4=0). The questionnaire of stress was in line with the study carried out in Nepal by Sreeramareddy et al. after few changes. The enlistment of was 30 potential stressors. The division was made into 3 different classification such as academic, health and psychosocial. For every single possible stressor, prevalence was categorised as “rarely/never”, “sometimes” and “always/often” and scores were awarded as 0,1 and 2 respectively by using Likert Scale (1-10). The objective and purpose of the research was told to all the participants. The guarantee was given with regard to confidentiality. The option of acceptance or refusal was given to all participants in the study. Students were given the questionnaires and were collected after duly completion by the researchers. SPSS version 22 software was used for analysing the data. There was calculation of mean perceived stress score and percentage of prevalence of every single potential stressor. For analysing the difference in mean perceived stress score in different categories, the ANOVA technique was used. For determining the core stress elements from general to specific approach, Binary Logistic Regression Analysis was performed. Value of P was set at 0.05.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics: 450 students out of 500 completed the questionnaire and returned it with total response rate of 90% (98.74% for 1st, and 97.5% for 2nd and 100% for 3rd, 4th and final years). The responders' mean age was 21.21 (SD=0.81).

Perceived Stress: Total perceived stress mean score was 21.32 (SD=5.21). Medical students of first year had significantly high stress and different

from others. Therefore, the current hypothesis is that students of initial years are more stressed, is proved.

Medical students of first year have shown that the highest stress levels are Most Potential Stressors. Most potential stressors were relating to academic stressor there were 39% prevalence and 31% prevalence of health stressor. The prevalence rate for psychological stressor was 30%. The potential stressors were ‘Frequency of Examinations’, ‘Performance In Examinations’, ‘Nutrition’, ‘Accommodation Away From Home’, ‘Satisfaction With Quality Of Food In Mess’, ‘Sleeping Difficulties’. All the most potential stressors from every year were from the academic domain. Therefore, the current hypothesis that Most Potential Stressors are from the academic domain is proved.

DISCUSSION

The evaluation and identification of source of perceived stress among the MBBS students (from year 1 to 5). Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10) questionnaire was used for calculation of perceived stress. The reason for selecting this scale was due to its documented reliability and viability. In the current study the total perceived stress mean score was 21.32 (SD=5.21) For the assessment of the perceived stress different researches have been carried out in the medical student with the use of PSS-10. In India the PSS score was assessed as 29.58 and in Pakistan it was 30.84. The calculated level of stress was very high as compared to calculations in the current study. A comparative study was carried out in Bangladesh for the assessment of different mean perceived stress between private and public medical institutions. 54% was calculated the overall perceived stress prevalence and there was significant statistical difference in the stress level between private and public medical institutions. The study limitation is that it could only include one institution. The focus of the future research must be on the assessment of level of stress in different institutions to address the issue on higher level. Different scales are used in numerous researches on stress. Different stress levels were found because different instruments were used for carrying out the researches or there could be real difference because of different backgrounds of socio-demography. Among the individual classes, the current study calculated PSS score and assessed the difference. The level of stress among first year students was comparatively high and different from others. There can be the reason that instant change from pre-medical to medical course and students may find it hard to

cover under the high pressure of study, different environment of study and away from home. The teachers comparatively are not very supportive, helpful or facilitating as school teacher and the counsellors are missing in the university. The most interesting part of the result of the current research was that the stress level decreases by the year advances. Similar results have been shown in the studies conducted in Canada and India. In Germany, different result had been found because of different socio-demographic backgrounds. In the current research, the most prevalent stressor was academic element relating to severity and frequency. Therefore, the second hypothesis of the current research that mostly the possible stressor affects the academic performance of medical undergraduates is proved. The most stressful event among them was "Frequency in Examination" and "Poor Performance in Examination". In India and Pakistan, different academic stressors were pointed out in different studies carried out. The most common academic stressor across the globe between both the studies was "increase frequency of examination". The medical institutions must work in this field and struggle to cope with this main issue which the students are facing. The psychosocial and health related most potential stressors are "Bad Nutrition", "Living Away From Home", "Low Quality Food in Mess" and "Lack of Sleep". Similar result has been reported by the studies conducted in different countries. The affected social life of a student restrain him to interact with people and prompt mostly to spend his time all alone. In the past couple of years sleeping disorder in the students have significantly increased. As per the study conducted in Pakistan's

medical college, medical student's sleep quality is badly affected by the stress and results in intake of sedative pills to cope the sleep disorder. All the undergraduate students of the current study were females because Fatima Jinnah Medical University is the University for women. Therefore, there is no stress comparison available between both sexes. The difference of level of stress between male and female medical student has been assessed in other studies. According to study carried out in Saudi Arabia it has been revealed that stress prevalence was high ($p < 0.5$) in females (75.7%) as compared to males (57%). Future researches must focus on including the different institution for performing comparison. It has been suggested that the medical institutions must provide guidance to students at the time of stress so to lead them of right path. This can be performed by the interaction between teacher student in healthy activity such as conference, sports, seminars, co-curriculum activities where students have time to express and control their complex.

CONCLUSION

The current research has revealed an increased perceived stress level in the MBBS fresh enrolling students. The most frequent stressor was the academic stressor which affect the complete performance of a student. It is imperative for medical institutions to appreciate the stress level and its difference reasons in medical students. It has been suggested that early guidance and regular assessment of stressors would help medical student to cope with academic deviations which may result in drop out from medical institution and get the students ready for stressful career of medicine.

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